

INTERNATIONAL DATA
SPACES ASSOCIATION

The Data Spaces Radar

Data Spaces Support Centre Edition

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Unveiling the next chapter: The enhanced Data Spaces Radar

Dear Readers,

It's evident that the Data Spaces Radar plays a fundamental role within the dynamic landscape of data spaces. With nearly 150 entries, it's clear that data spaces are no longer a concept confined to theory but in some cases tangible reality on a global scale. Thanks to the pioneering efforts of International Data Spaces Association (IDSA), the conversation has shifted from defining data spaces to enhancing their interoperability and realizing the potential of a sovereign data economy worldwide.

To keep pace with this ever-evolving landscape, it was essential to rebuild the Data Spaces Radar. The new version is not just a facelift but a significant milestone, elevating the radar to a more professional tool essential for extending its relevance and amplifying its benefits for industry. The tool is now hosted and maintained by the International Data Spaces Association with additional showcase contributions of the Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC) community.

Therefore, the first Data Spaces Radar Report of 2024 not only highlights the new radar and its enhanced features but also presents the crucial role of the DSSC and its vibrant Community of Practice – a community of data spaces on its way to become operational and changing the way data is shared in different domains. Together with these pioneers we are looking forward to shape the future data economy.

Sincerely,

Christoph Mertens
Head of Adoption

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The new Data Spaces Radar in the spotlight

More than two years back, the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) introduced the groundbreaking Data Spaces Radar, a tool that swiftly gained acclaim and found its place within the dynamic landscape of data spaces. Today, we are excited to unveil the evolution of this pioneering asset – the newly enhanced Data Spaces Radar.

The Data Spaces Radar serves as the central repository for all data space endeavors. It is an accessible tool designed to

provide a comprehensive view of various data space initiatives worldwide. Offering insights into the 18 different sectors, global expansion, technical transparency and new stages of development of the data spaces featured in the radar.

Since the inception of this asset by IDSA, the Data Spaces Radar has cataloged nearly 150 entries.

New features

Improved user experience

1

Get ready to spend hours navigating effortlessly with a better look and feel, promising an enriched user experience.

Increased capacity

2

Hosting more data spaces and use cases, the radar expands its capabilities to accommodate the ever-growing data spaces ecosystem.

Enhanced visualization

3

Beyond the classic radar view, explore charts, graphs, and various visualization options for a deeper understanding of data space examples.

4

Advanced filtering

Experience refined search functionalities with free-form searches and diverse filters based on categories, allowing you to find exactly what you're looking for.

5

Global reach

Crossing borders, the radar showcases data space examples from around the world. Get ready for a comprehensive geographical overview with a map highlighting data spaces on all continents.

6

Technical transparency

Dive into the components; understand what data spaces are made of by exploring the technical building blocks, implemented connector or component in the ecosystem of the International Data Spaces.

The five development stages of a data spaces journey

New maturity indicators

Exploratory Stage

This is the development stage in which a data space initiative starts. Typically, in this stage, a group of people begins to explore the interest, potential and viability of a data space. The exploratory activities may include, among others: identifying and attracting interested stakeholders, collecting requirements, discussing use cases, or reviewing existing conventions or standards.

Preparatory Stage

This development stage starts when a data space initiative has a critical mass of committed partners, and there is an agreement to move forward with the initiative and proceed towards creating a data space. It is typical for this stage that such partners jointly develop use cases and prepare to implement the data space.

Implementation Stage

This development stage starts when a data space initiative has a sufficiently detailed project plan, milestones, and resources (funding and other) for developing its governance framework and infrastructure in the context of a data space pilot. It is typical for this stage that the parties involved in the pilot and the value created for each are also clearly identified.

Operational Stage

This development stage starts when a data space initiative has a tested implementation of infrastructure(s) and governance framework, and the first use case becomes operational (data flowing between data providers and data recipients and use case providing the intended value). Typically, in this stage, changes occur, both in the governance framework and the technical implementation of the data space.

Scaling Stage

This development stage starts when a data space initiative has proven to gain new participants and embrace new use cases consistently and organically. In this stage, the data space can realistically be expected to be financially and operationally sustainable and respond to market changes and grow over time.

Why put your use case on the Data Spaces Radar?

By featuring your use case on the Data Spaces Radar, you gain visibility and recognition within the data community and attract potential partners, investors, and customers. It encourages knowledge sharing and collaboration among organizations. And you can inspire others to explore innovative approaches to data-driven solutions. You may spark new ideas.

The Data Spaces Radar enables companies to compare their use case with others. This can provide insights for improvement and optimizations. As part of the radar community, you can connect with other data experts and stakeholders. By fostering networking opportunities, you also invite constructive feedback from peers, leading to continued refinement of your project.

And not to forget: By sharing your use case, you contribute to the growth and development of the entire data ecosystem.

Register here

Public Sector

2

Skills and Education

3

Logistics

10

Language

1

Cultural heritage

1

Accelerating data spaces: The role of the Data Spaces Support Centre

Funded by the European Commission under the Digital Europe Programme, the Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC) will coordinate relevant actions that strive towards common European data spaces. It aims to foster collaboration, innovation, and growth within the data space ecosystem by offering support services, including technical expertise, project management assistance, and access to relevant networks and resources. The DSSC explores the needs of data space initiatives, defines common requirements and establish best practices to accelerate the formation of sovereign data spaces as a crucial element of digital transformation in all areas. With the combined expertise of 12 consortium partners in the project, the Data Spaces Support Centre provides the best possible support to data space initiatives on the requirements related to interoperable data spaces. With that, the DSSC plays a pivotal role in contributing to the realization of the European Union's vision for common European data spaces.

With the Data Spaces Support Centre, we have taken a major step into the future. Data spaces are, by their nature, a joint endeavor. We are not building data spaces for our own self-interest. We are building them to have smart services that make peoples' lives better, make businesses more profitable, and drive innovation in Europe.

Lars Nagel, CEO of International Data Spaces Association

Get to know the heartbeat of the data spaces community

The European pursuit of fair, compliant, and trustworthy data spaces relies on a collaborative approach involving a diverse array of participants. Led by the DSSC, this effort aims to foster a strong network of participants, comprising organizations and initiatives dedicated to data space development.

Central to this network is the Community of Practice (CoP), which includes a set of existing and emerging data space initiatives and the set of (potential) data space building block implementers, particularly those participating in the SIMPL initiative. These are organizations, project consortiums, and networks of committed partners who work together to implement data spaces in various sectors.

Ready to join the data spaces world?

All data space initiatives are encouraged to register for the Data Spaces Radar and to actively engage with the DSSC and leading projects dedicated to common European Data spaces. This collective effort is essential for realizing the objectives set forth by the EU Data Strategy and facilitating transformative impacts across the European economy, industry, and society.

Enter the world of data spaces initiatives!

Now that we grasp the essence of the Community of Practice, anticipation mounts for the unveiling of its tangible outcomes and insights. Within this report, we highlight select Community of Practice members hailing from diverse sectors like smart communities, manufacturing, health, and language. This proves the varied landscape of data spaces and the Community of Practice's cross-domain mission to proliferate them across Europe.

With the support of the Data Spaces Support Centre and its initiatives, we anticipate a significant boost in the right direction: towards establishing a fair and sovereign data economy, underpinned by the IDS standard.

Enjoy exploring the Community of Practice.

European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI)

Providing access to genomic data to improve research, policy making and healthcare across Europe

Challenge

The full roll-out of personalized medicine across Europe hinges on the integration of high-quality genomics and health data alongside other data types, such as social and economic data. Only through this integration can we lay the groundwork for personalized prevention, diagnostics, and treatment, enhancing citizens' and patients' quality of life while reducing overall healthcare system costs. This approach will have a profound impact on various disease areas, including rare diseases, cancer, common and complex diseases, and infectious diseases, aligning with EHDS, EC missions, partnerships, and goals.

Success

The European genomic data spaces will provide access to this high-quality data collection distributed across 24 countries for researchers (in academia and industry), innovators and policy-makers to generate new knowledge that can be transformed into innovation to be applied within the healthcare system and drive the evolution of the applicable policies.

+ Benefits

- » *Researchers, innovators and policymakers from Europe or third countries could get access to a high-quality virtual cohort that greatly facilitates the identification of data that fits their study needs.*
- » *Benefit for the healthcare system by the development of new methods for personalized prevention, diagnosis, and treatment.*

GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

Scan for more info

Building a data-driven future for cancer care

Challenge

Health data, including medical images, are highly distributed and fragmented in Europe. Artificial Intelligence (AI) offers a paradigm shift towards data-driven decision making that is revolutionizing medicine. In medical imaging, an increasing number of studies are appearing in which AI tools are making important contributions towards a more accurate diagnosis or a more reliable treatment response and prognostic prediction. However, there can be a significant difference between the design and the real-world performance of algorithms, leading to ethical and safety issues.

Success

EUCAIM aims to tackle this issue by conducting well-designed research on data, observational clinical studies, and supporting AI development trained and validated on a large volume of images. It requires an infrastructure for accessing standardized images of patients with various cancer types and related patient data for basic and clinical research. This comprehensive research infrastructure involves multiple data ecosystems and heterogeneous databases across European, national, and regional levels. Cases are recruited from real-world environments and finalized clinical trials, encompassing diverse imaging modalities, protocols, and additional data and metadata. The EUCAIM infrastructure will ensure full interoperability with other components of the European Health Data Space (EHDS).

Benefits

- » *Facilitated compliance with EHDS regulation*
- » *Engagement in large-scale, multicentric cancer-fighting studies*
- » *Enhanced visibility and prestige*
- » *Access to a vast, diverse dataset*

European Federation for Cancer Images (EUCAIM) is co-funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement 101100633.

Scan for more info

European Data Space for Smart Communities

The large-scale cross-sectorial data space to support policy priorities of cities and communities within Europe

Challenge

The public and private sector encounter various data sharing challenges, including ensuring the privacy and security of citizen/customer data, integrating disparate systems for interoperability, navigating complex legal and regulatory frameworks, and maintaining data quality standards. The main challenge lies in extracting value from data and aligning public and private interests to foster mutually beneficial outcomes for society.

Success

The blueprint from the European Data Space for Smart Communities outlines a multi-stakeholder governance scheme, a catalogue of specifications, a reference architecture, and a roadmap. These components are designed to facilitate the development of trustworthy local data ecosystems, harmonize them into a European data space, and support cities and communities in transitioning to this digital landscape. This framework targets stakeholders from public and private sectors, scientific communities, and civil society organizations.

+ Benefits

- » *By facilitating seamless data sharing and integration, the data space enhances the efficiency of smart community initiatives, allowing for better-informed decision-making and resource allocation.*
- » *Access to a wealth of diverse data sources fosters innovation within smart communities, driving the development of novel solutions and services to address urban challenges more effectively.*
- » *With better data access and analysis capabilities, smart communities can implement more sustainable practices and policies, such as optimizing energy usage, reducing waste, and promoting eco-friendly transportation.*

European Data Space for Smart Communities is funded by the European Union Digital Europe Work Programme 2021-2022 under Grant Agreement No. 101123342.

Scan for more info

Common European Language Data Space

Fostering the trustworthy exchange of language data

Challenge

AI-based tools have gained significant importance, impacting daily life and driving trends like the rise of language-centric AI in tools such as ChatGPT and search engines like Bing. Language data is crucial for the creation of state-of-the-art Language Technology (LT) and Natural Language Processing (NLP) applications. Many LT providers face challenges in collecting the necessary amount of language data required for the development of competitive language-centric AI. A common language data space is seen as key to fostering a sustainable data ecosystem, promoting innovation and research.

Success

The European Language Data Space (LDS) develops the digital European marketplace for language data and other language resources. The LDS infrastructure will provide stakeholders with easy access to free or commercial high-quality data and offer a data sharing platform for research. Additionally, it will enable data owners to monetize their data, facilitate the exchange of best practices and insights with other stakeholders and support finding new partners and collaboration opportunities through a single, EU-compliant platform.

Components

- » The LDS infrastructure is currently being developed; the first prototype will be made available in mid-2024. The Language Data Space Connector will be based on the Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC).

Benefits

- » *Data owners can monetize language data and models while adhering to European values and EU regulations.*
- » *Users can connect with stakeholders via the European Language Data Space.*
- » *The European Language Data Space aids in developing multilingual and multimodal language technologies and language-centric AI.*

The Common European Language Data Space is funded under contract LC-01936389 with the European Union under the DIGITAL Work Programme 2021-2022.

Scan for more info

TEMS – Trusted European Media Data Space

Scan for more info

Building a resilient data-driven ecosystem in the media sector

Challenge

The media industry faces challenges stemming from fragmented data sources, data security concerns, evolving revenue models, and the demand for personalized content experiences. Establishing a media data space addresses these challenges by providing a secure environment for integrating data, enhancing privacy measures, and exploring new revenue streams. It empowers media companies to navigate digital transformation effectively and deliver engaging content tailored to consumer preferences while ensuring data sovereignty.

Success

TEMS aims to develop a secure data ecosystem for media companies, that's grounded on a technical infrastructure with governance mechanisms to ensure an easy, cross-border access to key datasets in the media sector, facilitating at the same time content co-generation, co-creation and co-distribution as well as transmedia/cross-media narratives. With that TEMS drives innovation and addresses digital economy challenges, such as regaining competitiveness against online platforms like the FAANG group (Facebook, Amazon, Apple, Netflix, Google).

+ Benefits

- » *Companies can leverage secure and trusted data sharing within TEMS to innovate dissemination and fact-checking, potentially leading to more accurate and reliable information delivery.*
- » *Access to comprehensive audience data enables personalized content delivery, fostering deeper engagement with audiences and opening avenues for new revenue streams.*
- » *Media companies can utilize TEMS for effective digital rights management, ensuring proper licensing, distribution, and protection of intellectual property.*

Funded by the Digital Europe Programme of the European Union Under Grant Agreement No 101123423.

SM4RTENANCE

SM4RTENANCE

Scan for more info

Trusted data sharing for manufacturing equipment industry

Challenge

The EU leads the global market for high-quality products, with European Industry dominating as the largest exporter of manufactured goods, accounting for 83% of EU exports. However, the current landscape, marked by increased Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, and Ambiguity (VUCA), poses challenges, especially for small and medium-sized companies. Climate change, supply chain disruption, and conflicts further intensify pressure for digital and ecological transformation across European industry. Yet, innovative data utilization and exchange in manufacturing could serve as a stabilizing force, fostering greater autonomy and sovereignty within the global manufacturing sector.

Success

SM4RTENANCE aims to create a cross-sectorial data space for Asset 4.0, enabling seamless data sharing throughout the asset lifecycle. It provides standardized APIs and a decentralized federated Operating System for easy integration, fostering competition on the application and business levels. By connecting key ecosystems and standards, SM4RTENANCE ensures growth and economies of scale for predictive maintenance and supply chain data spaces, following common European data space principles.

+ Benefits

- » *Sectorial unification: SM4RTENANCE facilitates alignment between national and EU manufacturing initiatives, fostering competitiveness and innovation.*
- » *Economic impact: By promoting data sharing among top EU manufacturers, SM4RTENANCE aims to unlock significant value, potentially reaching billions of euros.*
- » *Continuity and integration: SM4RTENANCE focuses on integrating data sources and advancing digital twin processes in digital engineering & manufacturing, ensuring seamless operations.*
- » *Data space facilitation: Beyond factory interoperability, SM4RTENANCE plays a pivotal role in enabling the deployment of data space 4.0, breaking barriers and fostering trust.*

Funded by
the European Union

This project is co-funded by the Digital Europe Programme of the European Union Under Grant Agreement No 101123423.

Scan for more info

Data space for manufacturing excellence

Challenge

Current data handling methods hinder industrial data use due to data silos and security issues while data sharing data across systems adds security risks. Specialized infrastructures are needed to unlock the full potential of this data, enabling new services, and boosting Industry 4.0 adoption. Medium-sized companies face additional challenges like labour-intensive data integration and lack of standardization. Overcoming data sovereignty concerns is crucial for widespread Industry 4.0 adoption, particularly in the data-driven European economy.

Success

UNDERPIN's mission is to develop an advanced platform for dynamic asset management and predictive/prescriptive maintenance. The UNDERPIN data space promotes cross-organizational data sharing while prioritizing data sovereignty. By fostering collaboration between SMEs and large industry players, the initiative aims to drive innovation and efficiency in the industry. Our solution includes interoperable data spaces, AI tools, FAIR datasets, and involvement from various stakeholders to optimize asset management processes. Tailored for European manufacturers in the refinery and renewable energy sectors, UNDERPIN is set to revolutionize data-driven solutions.

+ Benefits

- » *Improving processes, cost structure and material management via beyond the state-of-the-art data analysis.*
- » *Ensuring higher performance, better insight on asset critically, reduced overall downtimes and maintenance costs, extended machine usage periods, improved future machine designs, new service models, improve production line operations, company-internal processes, increased usability.*
- » *Enhancing business opportunities for industrial data value added services, supporting the transition towards circular economy.*

This project has received funding from the Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement No 101123179.

Take a closer look at what's on the radar: successful usage scenarios and inspiring data spaces

From manufacturing's supply chain to the automotive infrastructure, from energy transition to AI application – the wide range of data spaces enriches all companies involved across many ecosystems.

<u>Name</u>		<u>Development Stage</u>	<u>Sectors</u>
agdatahub	CoP	Implementation	Agriculture / Agrifood
Agriculture robot fleets and AI -as-a-service in FlexiGroBots project	Use Case	Implementation	Agriculture / Agrifood
AgriDataSpace	CoP	Preparatory	Agriculture / Agrifood
DjustConnect	Data space	Implementation	Agriculture / Agrifood
FutureForest	Data space	Implementation	Agriculture / Agrifood
iDDEN, International Dairy Data Exchange Network	Data space	Preparatory	Agriculture / Agrifood
Catena-X	Data Space	Operational	Automotive
Collaborative Warranty and Quality Management	Use Case	Preparatory	Automotive
GDSO	Data Space	Scaling	Automotive
Light Commercial Vehicles	Use Case	Implementation	Automotive
Post-Platforms for automotive	Data Space	Preparatory	Automotive
Supply Chain Manager	Use Case	Implementation	Automotive
EUROPEANA	CoP	Implementation	Cultural heritage
Basque Energy Cluster	Use Case	Preparatory	Energy
Carbon Capture Audit Trail (CAST / Trust Trail)	Use Case	Preparatory	Energy
Data and service marketplace for energy flexibility management	Use Case	Preparatory	Energy
Data Cellar	CoP	Preparatory	Energy

<i>Name</i>		<i>Development Stage</i>	<i>Sectors</i>
EDDIE - European Distributed Data Infrastructure for Energy	CoP	Preparatory	Energy
Energy Data Space (EnDaSpace)	Data Space	Implementation	Energy
Energy Use Case (Vienna, Austria)	Use Case	Exploratory	Energy
ENERSHARE	CoP	Preparatory	Energy
Green Data Hub – DIO: Data Space Energy Transition	Data Space	Preparatory	Energy
H2 Metaverse	Use Case	Exploratory	Energy
int:net - Interoperability Network for the Energy Transition	CoP	Preparatory	Energy
OMEGA-X	CoP	Preparatory	Energy
Offshore Energy Data Trust	Use Case	Preparatory	Energy
PLATOON: Smart Grids	Use Case	Implementation	Energy
PLATOON: Wind Energy	Use Case	Implementation	Energy
Post Platforms for Renewable Energy	Data Space	Preparatory	Energy
Solar Charge API	Use Case	Preparatory	Energy
Vehicle Charging	Use Case	Exploratory	Energy
Wind and Solar Assets modeling	Use Case	Exploratory	Energy
Wind Energy Generation Data Space	Use Case	Implementation	Energy
Data spaces for smart energy	Use Case	Exploratory	Energy
CADS - Carbon Agri Data Space	Data Space	Preparatory	Green Deal / Circular Economy
DaCapo - Circularity for a digitally-driven European manufacturing	Use Case	Preparatory	Green Deal / Circular Economy
Data Sharing Coalition - Green Loans	Use Case	Preparatory	Green Deal / Circular Economy
Green Data Hub – DIO: Data Space Digital Climate Twin	Data Space	Exploratory	Green Deal / Circular Economy
Green Deal Dataspace	Data Space	Operational	Green Deal / Circular Economy
The ENES Data Space	Use Case	Preparatory	Green Deal / Circular Economy
The Green Deal Data Space Foundation and its Community of Practice (GREAT)	Cop	Preparatory	Green Deal / Circular Economy
EUropean Federation for CAncer IMages (EUCAIM)	CoP	Implementation	Health
Gatekeeper	Use Case	Preparatory	Health
Genomics Data Infrastructure	CoP	Implementation	Health
HEALTH-X dataLOFT	Data Space	Preparatory	Health
Medical Data Space MedDS	Use Case	Implementation	Health
NL AI Coalition - Oncology Research	Use Case	Preparatory	Health
VELES Project (HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ACCESS-04 – 101087483)	Use Case	Exploratory	Health
European Language Data Space (LDS)	CoP	Preparatory	Language
AI.SOV	Use Case	Implementation	Logistic

<u>Name</u>		<u>Development Stage</u>	<u>Sectors</u>
DASLOGIS - Dutch Data Spaces for Logistics	Data Space	Implementation	Logistic
GlobShare	Use Case	Preparatory	Logistic
Green Data Hub – DIO: Data Space Circular Economy	Data Space	Exploratory	Logistic
Horizontal Supply Chain Collaboration	Use Case	Implementation	Logistic
Industrial Additive Manufacturing Services	Use Case	Implementation	Logistic
ONCITE	Use Case	Implementation	Logistic
Post-Platforms for Supply Chain	Data Space	Preparatory	Logistic
Silicon Economy	Data Space	Preparatory	Logistic
Smart Connected Supplier Network	Data Space	Operational	Logistic
Aixa	Data Space	Preparatory	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
AluTrace	Use Case	Implementation	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
Boost 4.0	Data Space	Implementation	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
Brainport Industries Smart Factory	Use Case	Implementation	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
Data Space 4.0	CoP	Preparatory	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
ECI Gatewise	Use Case	Operational	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
FA ³ ST ecosystem for I4.0-compliant and data-sovereign digital twins	Use Case	Implementation	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
I4.0 data space and app marketplace for connected factories and service providers	Use Case	Implementation	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
Increased visibility of order delivery process	Data Space	Implementation	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
Logistics and Product Life Cycle Management	Use Case	Exploratory	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
ManuSpace	Data Space	Preparatory	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
MARKET4.0: 3DFORM	Use Case	Implementation	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
MARKET4.0: ENTER Experiment	Use Case	Implementation	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
Metal Domain Data Space - Market 4.0	Data Space	Implementation	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
Mondragon Assembly Egokia	Use Case	Implementation	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
NTT Testbed on Data Governance and Sovereignty Across Countries and Companies	Use Case	Implementation	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
Plastic Domain Data Space – Market 4.0	Use Case	Implementation	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
Post-Platforms for Manufacturing	Data Space	Preparatory	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
Pressious Data Space	Data Space	Implementation	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
Qu4lity - Manufacturing Process Anomaly Detection for Capital Goods in Automotive and Railway Sectors	Use Case	Implementation	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
Smart Factory	Use Case	Preparatory	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
Smart Factory Web	Use Case	Implementation	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
Sm4rtenance	Data Space	Implementation	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0

<u>Name</u>		<u>Development Stage</u>	<u>Sectors</u>
UCIMU „Data Space Committee“	Data Space	Exploratory	Manufacturing / Industry 4.0
Data Space for Multimodal Passenger Mobility	Data Space	Preparatory	Mobility
EdgeDS	Use Case	Exploratory	Mobility
Gaia-X4KI	Data Space	Implementation	Mobility
Green Data Hub – DIO: Data Space Mobility Transition	Data Space	Exploratory	Mobility
Kiel Mobility Digital Twin	Use Case	Implementation	Mobility
Mobility Data Space	Data Space	Operational	Mobility
Mobilithek	Data Space	Operational	Mobility
Post-Platforms for mobility	Data Space	Preparatory	Mobility
Preparatory actions for the data space for mobility	CoP	Preparatory	Mobility
Rail Data Space	Use Case	Preparatory	Mobility
Reallab Hamburg	Use Case	Implementation	Mobility
Würth C-Part Supply	Use Case	Exploratory	Mobility
Advaneo DMP	Data Space	Operational	Other
Bauhaus.MobilityLab	Use Case	Implementation	Other
Cross-domain: Web 3.0 Data Space	Data Space	Preparatory	Other
DataPorts	Use Case	Preparatory	Other
Defense Data Space	Data Space	Implementation	Other
DigiChecks: Construction Data Space for Building Permit Management	Data Space	Implementation	Other
Deutsche Telekom - Data Intelligence Hub	Data Space	Operational	Other
EUHubs4Data (EUH4D)	Use Case	Implementation	Other
EuProGigant - European Production Giganet	Use Case	Preparatory	Other
FAIR Data Spaces	Use Case	Preparatory	Other
MERLOT	Data Space	Preparatory	Other
Green Data Hub – DIO: Data Space Tourism	Data Space	Preparatory	Other
Huawei Data Space	Data Space	Operational	Other
IDEAS - Integrated Engineering dAta Sharing	Use Case	Preparatory	Other
IDSA Data Space - Kubernetes Deployment Scenario	Data Space	Exploratory	Other
iGreenPort	Data Space	Implementation	Other
KI Marktplatz (AI Marketplace)	Use Case	Implementation	Other
Macau-EU Cross-Border Flow of Scientific Research Data	Use Case	Preparatory	Other
Maritime Data Space	Data Space	Implementation	Other
MARKET4.0 Marketplace	Use Case	Implementation	Other

<u>Name</u>		<u>Development Stage</u>	<u>Sectors</u>
Ö-Cloud	Data Space	Implementation	Other
Orbiter/idento.one	Use Case	Implementation	Other
PwC Data Ecosystem	Data Space	Exploratory	Other
Resilience Data Space (HERAKLION)	Data Space	Preparatory	Other
SCUNY (School – UNited – Economy)	Use Case	Preparatory	Other
Software Dataspace	Use Case	Exploratory	Other
Sovity Data Space	Data Space	Operational	Other
The European Legal Data Space Nucleus	Use Case	Exploratory	Other
truzzt box	Use Case	Operational	Other
truzzt Port	Use Case	Operational	Other
Trusted Exchange for Aeronautics	Use Case	Implementation	Other
TRUSTEE - Trust and privacy preserving computing platform for cross-border federation of data	Data Space	Preparatory	Other
Public Procurement Data Space (PPDS)	Data Space	Implementation	Public Sector
The Once-Only Technical System (OOTS)	Data Space	Scaling	Public Sector
Data Space for Skills (DS4Skills)	CoP	Preparatory	Skills and Education
Open Access Book Usage Data Trust (OAeBU DT)	Use Case	Preparatory	Skills and Education
PAIRS	Use Case	Preparatory	Skills and Education
City Dataspace	Data Space	Implementation	Smart Cities
DS4SSCC	CoP	Preparatory	Smart Cities
GATE Urban Data Space	Use Case	Exploratory	Smart Cities
Intelligent Washing Machine	Use Case	Implementation	Smart Cities
MyData for Cities	Use Case	Preparatory	Smart Cities
PLATOON: Smart Buildings	Use Case	Implementation	Smart Cities
Post-Platforms for Smart City	Data Space	Preparatory	Smart Cities
Smart Parking	Use Case	Implementation	Smart Cities
The Smart Building Dataspace	Data Space	Preparatory	Smart Cities
Tidy City	Use Case	Preparatory	Smart Cities
Trusted Data Sharing in Smart Cities	Use Case	Implementation	Smart Cities
Dates	CoP	Preparatory	Tourism
Preparatory Actions for the Data Space for Tourism (DSFT)	CoP	Preparatory	Tourism

Get to know DSSC's Community of Practice

Common Europe data space for cultural heritage

Cultural heritage

European Federation for CANCER IMages (EUCAIM)

Health

Interoperability Network for the Energy Transition (IntNET)

Interoperability / Energy

Language Data Space (LDS)

Language

Prep. action Agriculture Data Space (AgriDataSpace)

Agriculture

Prep. action Green Deal (GREAT)

Green

Prep. action Manufacturing Data Space (EU DATA SP4CE)

Manufacturing

The European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI)

Health (Genomics)

CDepl. action for the Data Space for Mobility (deployEMDS)

Mobility

Depl. action for the Data space for Manufacturing (UNDERPIN)

Manufacturing

Depl. action Data Space for Smart Communities (DS4SSCC-DEP)

Smart cities

Depl. action for the Data space for Manufacturing (SMARTENANCE)

Manufacturing

Depl. action for the Data Space for Media (TEMS)

Media

(Prometheus-X)

Skills

Establishing the grounds for a common European energy data space

Energy

Establishing the grounds for a common European energy data space

Energy

Establishing the grounds for a common European energy data space

Energy

Establishing the grounds for a common European energy data space

Energy

Establishing the grounds for a common European energy data space

Energy

Previously part of CoP

Prep. action
Tourism Data Space
(DATES)

Tourism

Prep. action
Tourism DataSpace
(DSFT)

Tourism

Prep. action
Skills Data Space
(DS4Skills)

Skills

Prep. action Smart
Communities Data Space
(DS4SSCC)

Smart cities

PrepDSpace4Mobility
Prep. action
Mobility Data Space
(PrepDSpace4Mobility)

Mobility

Community of Practice

Discover all Data Spaces
Radar Reports

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